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THE IMPORTANCE OF IDENTIFYING AND SET IN PLACE A LAW OR ARBITRATION AGREEMENT, SAUDI ARABIA LAW STUDY

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First research

Practical applications of the importance of the appointment of the place in Saudi arbitration system

For the record, to determine and set the place of great importance , as has been explained in Section former arbitration laws as follows to determine and set the place to determine the applicable law and the identity of the judgment as well as the type of arbitration and the extent of undergoing public order prevailing in the place of arbitration , as well as take advantage of the means of communication available at that location.

The parade will be practical applications to determine the place and its importance in Saudi arbitration system in the following points:

First, Article II of the system

Article II of the arbitration system Saudi Ali that he (Without prejudice to the provisions of Islamic law and the provisions of international conventions to which the Kingdom is a party, shall apply this system to all arbitration , whatever the nature of the relationship irregular , which revolves around the conflict , if you were this arbitration in the Kingdom. or international commercial arbitration was conducted abroad , and agreed to Partyah subject to the provisions of this system.

Does not apply the provisions of this order on disputes relating to personal status , and issues that may not be where the Magistrate .) (82(

The importance of determining the place in this article are as follows:

1- Determine the spatial jurisdiction to apply the provisions of the Arbitration Arbitration is all being in the Kingdom.

2- as well as the subject of an international commercial arbitration all agree Partyah Ali subjected to Saudi arbitration system spatially subject to the jurisdiction of the arbitration system in Saudi Arabia.

3- The idea of a limitation contained Article Without prejudice to the provisions of Islamic law and the provisions of international agreements to which the Kingdom is a party resulting from the fact that the Kingdom apply the provisions of Islamic Sharia in all disputes that take place on its territory , a type of vulnerability vital force of the provisions of the law.

1- Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH material No. 2.

Second, Article III of the Rules of

Article III of the same system that: (a international arbitration ruling in this system if the subject matter relates to international trade dispute , and in the following circumstances:

2- If the main center of the work of each of the parties to the arbitration is located in more than one country at the conclusion of the arbitration agreement , if a party has several business centers lesson place most closely associated with the subject of the dispute , and if not for one of the parties to the arbitration , or both, business center specific lesson habitual residence.

2- If the main center of the work of each of the parties to the arbitration is located in the same state at the conclusion of the arbitration agreement , and it was one of the places the following statement is situated outside this state :

- the place of arbitration as the same arbitration agreement , or pointed out how his appointment.
- Place an essential aspect of the implementation of the obligations arising from the business relationship between the parties.
- the place most closely associated with the subject of the dispute.

3-If the parties to resort to arbitration organization, or a permanent tribunal, or arbitration center based outside the Kingdom.

4- If the subject of the dispute covered by an arbitration agreement is linked to more than one state .) (8)

The importance of determining the place in this article are as follows:

1- Determine the type of arbitration and being internationally or not.

2-all the criteria for determining the type of international arbitration related to the idea of the place , including:

A - the main center of the work of each of the parties to the arbitration.

B - habitual residence.

C - the place of arbitration.

3- Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 3.

D - place an essential aspect of the implementation of the commitments.

E - the place most closely associated with the subject.

It is clear so that all the criteria for determining the type linked to the idea of the place of arbitration , which underlines the importance of recruiting the place.

Third, Article V of the system

Article V provides: If a party to the arbitration agreed to subject their relationship to the provisions of any document Oakd typical , or international convention or others) , shall act under the provisions of this document , including covered by special provisions of the arbitration, and that not contrary to the provisions of Islamic Sharia . (84(

Shown here is the importance of identifying the place not to breach the provisions of Islamic law applicable to the territory of the Kingdom.

Fourth: Article VI of the

Article VI and provides for- :

1- If there is no special agreement between the parties to the arbitration regarding the notifications are delivered reporting to the consignee personally - or his - or sent to the mailing address specified in the contract replaced the dispute , or specified in the charter party arbitration , or in the document governing the relationship that covered by arbitration.

2- If you can not be delivered to the consignee reported in accordance with paragraph (1) , is the delivery has been reported if a registered letter to the last place of business, or usual place of residence , or postal address known to the addressee.

3-do not apply the provisions of this article notifications of special courts invalidating the arbitration ruling before the courts.

The importance of place here in the delivery of notifications in the mailing address or habitual residence of one of the parties to the arbitration.

3-Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 5.

4-Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 6.

Fifth: Article VIII of the system

Article VIII Ali:

*have the jurisdiction to hear a suit invalidity of the arbitration award and matters referred by the system to the competent court Macoda Court of Appeals originally competent to hear the dispute.

*If the international commercial arbitration , both were in the Kingdom or abroad , so the jurisdiction of the Court of Appeal originally competent to hear the dispute in the city of Riyadh , unless otherwise agreed by the parties to the arbitration court of appeal in another kingdom. Through this article is clear and evident that the spatial jurisdiction of the court

having jurisdiction over the lawsuit invalidity of the arbitration award is the same jurisdiction and venue of the appeals court originally competent to hear the dispute.

As shall have jurisdiction and venue of the Court of Appeal in the city of Riyadh originally competent to hear the dispute if a trade dispute was whether internationally or outside the Kingdom.

Sixth: Article Avhashr of the system

Article XV Ali:

* the parties to the arbitration agreement on the choice of arbitrators , if not agree , follow the following:

•If the arbitral tribunal composed of one arbitrator chosen came to the competent court.

•If the arbitral tribunal composed of three arbitrators chose each party arbitrator with him , and then agree arbitrators to choose a third arbitrator , if not appointed by one party arbitrator within fifteen days following the receipt of a request from the other party, or if you do not agree arbitrators appointed on the choice of arbitrator third , within fifteen days following the date set most recently , took the competent court chosen at the request of interested accelerate , and within fifteen days from the date of submission of the application , and be the arbitrator chosen by the two arbitrators appointed or chosen by the competent court Presidency of the arbitral tribunal , shall apply these provisions in the case of the formation of the tribunal more than three arbitrators.

1- Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 8.

2- If you do not agree on the parties to the arbitration procedure for the selection of arbitrators , or Khalvha one of the parties , or two arbitrators appointed can not agree on is what is required by their agreement , or if the third party fails to perform what was entrusted to him in this regard , came to the competent court - at the request of interested accelerate - to do the procedure , or the work required , unless

otherwise provided in the agreement on how the other to complete this action or work.

3- take into account the competent court in the arbitrator chosen by the conditions stipulated by the agreement of the parties , and that the conditions required by this system , and the selection of the arbitrator shall issue its decision within thirty days from the date of submission of the application.

4- Without prejudice to the provisions of Articles (forty-ninth) and (session) of this system , the decision of the competent court to appoint an arbitrator in accordance with paragraphs (1 and 2) of this article , is unchallengeable in the independence , by any method of appeal. (87(

Through this article it is clear that the process of selection of arbitrators or any other action not agreed upon by the parties held the competent court as Article to the competent court here is the court which specializes originally hear the dispute if not offered arbitration and is subject to determine the competence of here to the same rules of jurisdiction spatial judicial former Signal them.

Also, the spatial jurisdiction is held to the competent court in other cases stipulated by 17,18,22,24,50,51,52,53,54 material from the system.

Seventh: Article XXV of the Rules of

Article (25) of the system: .

1- the parties to the arbitration agreement on the procedures followed by the arbitral tribunal , including Hakehma in subjecting these actions to the rules in force in any organization , or body , or arbitration center in the Kingdom or abroad , provided they do not violate the provisions of the Islamic Sharia.

2- If there is no such agreement was the arbitral tribunal - taking into account the provisions of Islamic law , and the provisions of this system - to choose the arbitration proceedings as it deems appropriate .

- *Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 15.

- *Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 25.

And here show the importance of place in the universe of the procedures followed by the tribunal must be subject to public order prevailing in the Kingdom and not violate the provisions of Islamic law applied them.

Eighth: Article XXVIII of the system

In addition, Article 28 of the Rules of Ali : the parties to the arbitration agreement on the place of arbitration in the Kingdom or abroad , if there is no agreement appointed by the arbitral tribunal the place of arbitration , taking into account the circumstances of the case, and convenient place for both sides , without prejudice to the authority of the arbitral tribunal may meet at any place it deems appropriate for consultation among its members , and to hear the statements of witnesses , or experts , or the parties to the dispute , or to preview the dispute , or to examine the documents , or see it.

This article explains the criteria by which to determine the place of arbitration is illustrated by the following:

1- the freedom of the parties to the arbitration agreement on the place of arbitration within or outside the Kingdom.

2- If there is no agreement of the parties to the arbitration based on the location of the arbitral tribunal to appoint the right place.

2- take into account the arbitral tribunal in the selection of the place of arbitration in case of disagreement by the circumstances of the case and place convenient to both parties.

IX : Article Thirty-eighth of the system

Article 38 of the rules on:

1- taking into account the non- violation of the provisions of Islamic law and public order in the Kingdom , the arbitral tribunal during the hearing of the dispute as follows:

•Apply the rules agreed by the parties to the arbitration on the merits of the dispute , and if they agreed to apply the system of a particular state followed the substantive rules without

rules on conflict of laws, unless otherwise agreed upon.

•If you do not agree on the parties to the arbitration statutes applicable to the subject of the dispute , the tribunal applied the substantive rules in the system who see it most relevant to the subject of the dispute.

8- Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 28.

.Must take into account when deciding the tribunal in terms of the contract at issue in dispute , and take into account the current mores in the type of transaction , and usages , and it was the interaction between the two parties.

2- If the parties to the arbitration agreed to expressly authorize the tribunal to conciliate it may be governed by appropriate according to the rules of justice and fairness .

It is clear from this article the importance of place in determining the rules applicable to the lawsuit or arbitration and dispute as follows :

-taking into account the non- violation of Islamic law applied in Saudi Arabia.

-apply the rules agreed upon by the parties on the subject of the dispute and apply the substantive rules in the state system that is agreed upon.

-If you do not agree on certain rules of the tribunal applied the substantive rules most relevant to the subject of the dispute in terms of location and public order and custom , and others.

-in all cases, must take into account the current mores in the type of transaction and the usages and happened upon deal between the two parties in the place of conflict.

Tenth: Forty-second article of the system

In addition, Article 42 of the Rules of Ali:

-The judgment of the arbitration shall be justified in writing , and signed by the arbitrators , and in the case of the formation of

the tribunal of more than one arbitrator, the signatures of a majority of the arbitrators shall suffice , provided that proof in the record of the case the reasons for not signing the minority.

-should include the arbitration award on the date of the pronouncement and place of issuance , and the names of opponents , and their addresses , and the names of the arbitrators , and their addresses , and nationalities , and their attributes , and a summary of the arbitration agreement , and a summary of statements and requests the parties to the arbitration , and their arguments , and their documents , and a summary report of the experience - if any - and the operative judgment , and to identify the arbitrators' fees , and expenses of the arbitration, and how they are distributed between the two parties , without prejudice ruled by Article (XXIV) of this system . (91(

- Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 38.

-Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 42.

The importance of locating the sentencing here in the identification of governance and its kind and being a national or a foreigner.

Eleventh : Article Fifty of the system

Article 50/2 of the system:

- requires the competent court considering a suit of nullity of its own invalidity of the arbitration award if it contains is contrary to the provisions of Islamic law and public order in the kingdom , or as agreed by the parties to the arbitration , or if it finds that the issue of conflict of issues that may not be arbitration under the present system .

This paragraph is unclear how closely to determine where public order prevails here in the Kingdom and the applicable provisions of Islamic law by being the cause of the invalidity of the arbitration award in the case of breach of any of them.

Twelfth : Article fifth session of the

Under article 55/2 of the system:

-it may not be the implementation of the arbitration award , according to the system only after verification of the following:

- it does not conflict with the judgment or decision issued by a court or committee or body which has jurisdiction over the subject of the dispute chapter in Saudi Arabia.

- It does not include what violates the provisions of Islamic law and public order in the Kingdom , and if possible segmentation rule with the promise of violation , may be the implementation of the remaining part is the violator.

- that he has been informed of the doomed notification thereof true. (93(

It is clear from this that it may not matter if the implementation of the arbitration award was inconsistent with the provisions of Islamic law or public order in the kingdom.

-Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 50/2.

-Saudi arbitration system issued by Royal Decree No. M / 34 dated 05/24/1433 AH item number 55/2.

The second topic

Practical applications of the importance of the appointment of the place of arbitration laws in comparison

The parade will be practical applications to determine the place and importance in the arbitration laws of Saudi law , a comparison of the Egyptian and Yemeni and Bahraini and Qatari and Sudanese as follows:

First requirement : Egyptian Arbitration Law

First: The first article of the law

Article I of the Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994 provides that: (Without prejudice to the provisions of international agreements in force in the Arab Republic of Egypt The provisions of this law, all arbitration between the parties of

persons of public law or private law , whatever the nature of the legal relationship that revolves around the conflict if such arbitration shall be in Egypt or international commercial arbitration was carried out on a limb and agreed to be subject to the provisions of this law . (94(

The importance of determining the place in this article are as follows:

- Determine the spatial jurisdiction to apply the provisions of the Arbitration Act and all arbitration is going on in Egypt.

- as well as the subject of an international commercial arbitration all agree Partyah on the subject to the Arbitration Act Egyptian spatially subject to the jurisdiction of the Arbitration Act Egyptian.

Second, Article III of the law

Article III of the Act provides that: (a rule in international arbitration law if this was the theme of a dispute relates to international trade and in the following circumstances:

- Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article 1.

First: If the main center of the work of each of the parties to the arbitration is located in two different states at the conclusion of the arbitration agreement if it was for one of the parties several business centers lesson place most closely associated with the subject of the arbitration agreement and if it is not a party to the arbitration business center lesson habitual residence.

Second: If the parties to resort to arbitration permanent arbitral organization or arbitration center is based within the Arab Republic of Egypt or abroad.

Third : If the subject of the dispute covered by an arbitration agreement is linked to more than one state.

Fourth, if the main center of the work of each of the parties to the arbitration is located in the same state time of the conclusion of the arbitration agreement was one of the following places is situated outside of this state.

)A) the place of arbitration as the same arbitration agreement or pointed out how his appointment.

)B) Place an essential aspect of the implementation of the obligations arising from the business relationship between the parties.

)C) the place most closely associated with the subject of the dispute .) (95(

The importance of determining the place in this article are as follows:

-Determine the type of arbitration and being internationally or not.

-all the criteria for determining the type of international arbitration related to the idea of the place , including:

A - the main center of the work of each of the parties to the arbitration.

B - habitual residence.

C - the place of arbitration.

D - place an essential aspect of the implementation of the commitments.

E - the place most closely associated with the subject.

-Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article No. 3.

It is clear so that all the criteria for determining the type linked to the idea of the place of arbitration , which underlines the importance of recruiting the place.

Third, Article VII of the law

Article VII of the Act :

1 - unless there is a special agreement between the parties to the arbitration be delivered any message or announcement to the addressee in person or in his office or in his habitual residence or mailing address known to the parties or specified in the charter party arbitration or in the document governing the relationship covered by the arbitration.

2 - If it is impossible to know one of these addresses after conducting the necessary investigations have been considered delivery if the ad a registered letter to the last place of business or habitual residence or your postal known to the addressee .

3 - do not apply the provisions of this article on the ads before the judicial courts . (96)

The importance of place here in the delivery of notifications in the mailing address or habitual residence of one of the parties to the arbitration.

Fourth: Article IX of the law

Article IX of the Act :

1 - have jurisdiction over arbitration issues referred by this law to the Egyptian judiciary, the court originally competent to hear the dispute but if the arbitration commercially internationally both were in Egypt or abroad , jurisdiction belongs to the Cairo Court of Appeal , unless the parties agree to the jurisdiction of the Court of Appeal again in Egypt .

2 - and continue to be held by the court has jurisdiction in accordance with the preceding paragraph without the other having jurisdiction until the end of all arbitration proceedings . (97)

15 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article No. 7 .

16 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article No. 9 .

Through this article is clear and evident that the spatial jurisdiction of the court having jurisdiction over the lawsuit invalidity of the arbitration award is the same jurisdiction and venue of the appeals court originally competent to hear the dispute .

Fifth: Article Seventeen of law

Article 17 provides :

1 - the parties to the arbitration agree on the selection of arbitrators and on how and when chosen , if not agree , follow the following:

(A) If the arbitral tribunal of the problem is governed by one took the court referred to in

Article (9) of this law chosen at the request of one of the parties .

(B) If the arbitral tribunal composed of three arbitrators chose each party arbitrator then agree arbitrators to choose the third arbitrator , if not appointed one of the parties the Court during the thirty days following the receipt of a request from the other party , or if you do not agree arbitrators appointed to choose the third arbitrator within the thirty days following the date of the appointment most recently took over the court referred to in Article (9) of this law chosen at the request of one of the parties and the arbitrator chosen by the two arbitrators appointed or chosen by the Court presidency of the arbitral tribunal shall apply these provisions in the case of the formation of the tribunal of more than a panel of three arbitrators .

2 - and if it goes against one of the parties procedures for the selection of arbitrators that they agreed or did not agree or did not agree arbitrators appointed an order which required their agreement it or if the failure of others to perform what was entrusted to him in this regard and came to the court referred to in Article (9) of this law at the request of one of the parties to the action or the work required unless otherwise provided in the agreement on how the other to complete this action or work .

3 - and take into account the court in the arbitrator chosen by the conditions required by this law and those that are agreed upon by the parties and issue its decision to choose the arbitrator expeditiously and without prejudice to the provisions of Articles (18, 19) of this law does not accept this decision challenged by any method of appeal. (98)

17 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article 17 .

Through this article it is clear that the process of selection of arbitrators or any other action not agreed upon by the parties held the competent court as Article to the competent court here is the court which specializes originally hear the dispute if not offered arbitration and is subject to determine the competence of here to the same rules of jurisdiction spatial judicial former Signal them.

Also, the spatial jurisdiction is held to the competent court in other cases stipulated by the rest of the articles of the law .

VI :: Article XXV of law

Article 25 of the law (the parties to the arbitration agreement on the procedures followed by the arbitral tribunal , including their right to subject these actions to the rules in force in any organization or arbitration center in the Arab Republic of Egypt or outside if there is no such agreement the arbitral tribunal , taking into account the provisions of this law to choose the arbitration proceedings as it deems appropriate .) (99)

And here show the importance of place in the universe of the procedures followed by the tribunal must be subject to public order prevailing in Egypt .

Seventh: Twenty- eighth article of the law

Article 28 provides : the parties to the arbitration agreement on the place of arbitration in Egypt or outside If there is no agreement appointed by the arbitral tribunal place of arbitration taking into account the circumstances of the case and the appropriate place for the parties without prejudice to the authority of the arbitral tribunal may meet at any place it deems appropriate to do conduct of arbitration proceedings Ksma parties to the dispute , witnesses or experts , or access to documents or preview the goods or funds , or conducting consultation among its members or otherwise. (100)

This article explains the criteria by which to determine the place of arbitration is illustrated by the following:

1 - the freedom of the parties to the arbitration agreement on the place of arbitration within Oforeign Egypt .

1 - If there is no agreement of the parties to the arbitration based on the location of the arbitral tribunal to appoint the right place .

18 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article 25 .

19 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article 28 .

3 - take into account the arbitral tribunal in the selection of the place of arbitration in case of disagreement by the circumstances of the case and place convenient to both parties .

Eighth: Thirty- ninth article of the law

Article 39 : 1 - applied by the arbitral tribunal rules on the subject of the dispute agreed to by the parties , and if they agreed to apply the law of a particular state followed the substantive rules without rules on conflict of laws unless otherwise agreed upon .

2 - If the parties do not agree on the legal rules applicable to the subject of the dispute by the arbitral tribunal applied the substantive rules of law which he considers most relevant to the dispute .

3 - must be sensitive to the arbitral tribunal in Chapter subject of the dispute in terms of the contract dispute and the current mores in the type of transaction .

4 - The arbitral tribunal may - if the parties expressly delegated arbitration conciliation - to decide on the merits of the dispute in accordance with the rules of justice and fairness without being bound by the provisions of the law . (101)

It is clear from this article the importance of place in determining the law applicable to the case of arbitration or dispute as follows :

1 - apply the rules agreed upon by the parties on the subject of the dispute and apply the substantive rules in the state system that is agreed upon .

2 - If you do not agree on certain rules of the tribunal applied the substantive rules most relevant to the subject of the dispute in terms of location and public order and custom , and others.

3 - In all cases, you must take into account the current mores in the type of transaction and the usages and run it to deal in place between the two parties to the conflict.

101 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article No. 39 .

IX : Article III of the Forty- law

Article 43 provides :

1 - The judgment of the arbitration in writing and signed by the arbitrators in the case of the formation of the tribunal of more than one arbitrator, the signatures of a majority of the arbitrators shall suffice , provided that proves the rule reasons for not signing the minority.

2 - must be causing the arbitration award unless the parties to arbitration agree otherwise or the law applicable to the arbitration proceedings are not required to cite reasons .

3 - must include the arbitration award on the names of litigants and their addresses and the names of arbitrators and their addresses , their nationalities, their attributes and the image of the arbitration agreement and a summary of the requests liabilities and their words and their documents and the verdict and the date and place of issue and its causes if mentioned duty . (102)

The importance of locating the sentencing here in the identification of governance and its kind and being a national or a foreigner .

Tenth: Fifty-third article of the law

Article 53/2 to :

2 - Under the court hearing the case of nullification of its own if the invalidity of the arbitration award is contrary to ensure public order in the Arab Republic of Egypt . (103)

This paragraph is unclear how closely to determine where public order prevails here in Egypt, being one of the reasons for the invalidity of the arbitration award in the case of breach .

102 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article No. 43 ..

103 - Egyptian Arbitration Law No. 27 of 1994, Article No. 53/2 .

The second requirement : the Arbitration Act Bahrain

First: The first article of the law

Article I , paragraph 1 and 2 of the Arbitration Act of Bahrain issued a decree law No. 9 of 1994 provides that:

1 - taking into account the provisions of international conventions in force in the State of Bahrain apply the provisions of this law on international commercial arbitration, unless the parties to the arbitration agreed to be subjected to another law .

With the exception of the provisions of Articles " 8, 9, 35.36 ," The provisions of this law , only if the place of arbitration is in the State of Bahrain . (104)

And show the importance of identifying the place in this article are as follows:

1 - Determine the spatial jurisdiction to apply the provisions of the Arbitration Act in all arbitration is being in the Kingdom of Bahrain .

2 - as well as the subject of an international commercial arbitration all agree Partyah on the subject to the Arbitration Act Egyptian spatially subject to the jurisdiction of the Arbitration Act of Bahrain.

The third and fourth paragraph of the first article has Nsta on :

3 - be arbitration internationally :

If a place of business of the parties to the arbitration agreement - the time of the conclusion of that agreement - and the reality in different States , or

B if one of the following places is situated outside the State in which the place of business of the parties :

" 1 " if the place of arbitration specified in the arbitration agreement or , according to him .

104 - Arbitration Act Bahrain issued a decree law No. 9 of 1994, Article 1 .

" 2 " is implemented anywhere where a substantial part of the obligations arising from the business relationship or the place where the subject matter of the dispute is most closely connected , or

C if the parties have expressly agreed that the subject of the arbitration agreement relates to more than one State .

4 - For the purposes of paragraph 3 of this article :

A. If a party has more of a place of business , so the lesson at the work most closely related to the arbitration agreement .

B If you do not work the headquarters of one of the parties shall be the lesson 's habitual residence . (105)

The importance of determining the place in this article are as follows :

1 - Determine the type of arbitration and being internationally or not.

2 - all the criteria for determining the type of international arbitration related to the idea of the place , including:

A - the workplace closer to the work of each of the parties to the arbitration .

B - habitual residence .

C - the place of arbitration .

E - the place most closely associated with the subject.

It is clear so that all the criteria for determining the type linked to the idea of the place of arbitration , which underlines the importance of recruiting the place.

105 - Arbitration Act Bahrain issued a decree law No. 9 of 1994, Article 1 .

Second, Article III of the law

Article III , paragraph 1 : Receipt of written communications :

1 - Unless the parties otherwise agree as follows:

(A) considers any messages written in the rule received if delivered to the addressee in person , or if delivered at work or at his place of residence or mailing address , and if you can not find on any of these places after making reasonable inquiry is a letter written in the rule received If sent to the last place of business or

habitual residence or mailing address , known to the addressee , and that under the letter recommended him or by any other means to try to prove them delivered . (106)

The importance of place here in the delivery of notifications and messages written in the mailing address or habitual residence or place of business for one of the parties to the arbitration.

Third, Article XXI of the Act

Article 21 on the place of arbitration :

1 - The parties are free to agree on the place of arbitration , if not agreed on the appointment of the tribunal came to this place to take into account the circumstances of the case , including work on the convenience of the parties .

2 - Notwithstanding the provisions of paragraph 1 of this Article, the arbitral tribunal may meet at any place it considers appropriate for consultation among its members and to hear the statements of witnesses , experts or the parties to the dispute or to preview the goods or other property , or to examine the documents , or otherwise, unless the parties agree otherwise. (107)

This article explains the criteria by which to determine the place of arbitration is illustrated by the following:

106 - Bahrain Arbitration Law issued by Decree Law No. 9 of 1994, Article 3/1 .

107 - Arbitration Act Bahrain issued a decree law No. 9 of 1994, Article No. 21 .

1 - the freedom of the parties to the arbitration agreement on the place of arbitration .

2 - If there is no agreement of the parties to the arbitration based on the location of the arbitral tribunal to appoint the right place .

3 - take into account the arbitral tribunal in the selection of the place of arbitration in case of disagreement by the circumstances of the case and place convenient to both parties .

Fourth: Article XXVIII of the law

Article 28 of the law : rules applicable to the subject of the dispute :

1 - arbitral tribunal shall decide the dispute according to the rules of law chosen by the parties as applicable to the subject of the dispute , and any choice of the law of a State or its legal system must be taken as a direct reference to the substantive law of that State and not to their own rules on conflict of laws, unless otherwise agreed the parties expressly agree otherwise.

2 - If the parties did not appoint any rules , the arbitral tribunal shall apply the law determined by the conflict of laws rules which it considers applicable .

3 - not the arbitral tribunal may adjudicate the dispute on an amicable basis , or on the appropriate rules of justice unless authorized parties have explicitly .

4 - in all cases, the arbitral tribunal shall decide the dispute in accordance with the terms of the contract and take into account the usages in the kind of commercial activity applicable to the transaction . (108)

It is clear from this article the importance of place in determining the law applicable to the case of arbitration or dispute as follows :

1 - apply the rules agreed upon by the parties on the subject of the dispute and apply the substantive rules in the state system that is agreed upon .

108 - Arbitration Act Bahrain issued a decree law No. 9 of 1994, Article 28 .

2 - If you do not agree on certain rules of the tribunal applied the substantive rules most relevant to the subject of the dispute in terms of location and public order and custom , and others.

3 - In all cases, you must take into account the current mores in the type of transaction and the usages and run it to deal in place between the two parties to the conflict.

Fifth: Article Thirty of law

Article 31/3 Ali : the decision must indicate the date of issuance and the place of arbitration

determined in accordance with paragraph (1) of Article "20", and the arbitration decision is issued in that place. (109)

The importance of locating the sentencing here in the identification of governance and its kind and being a national or a foreigner.

Sixth: Thirty-fourth article of the law

Article 34 / B on the abolition of the rule of arbitration cases :

B - If the court finds that :

1 - The subject of the dispute does not accept the settlement by arbitration under the law of the State of Bahrain .

2 - that the award is in conflict with the public policy of the State of Bahrain . (110)

This paragraph is unclear how closely to determine where here the public order situation in Bahrain and being one of the reasons for the invalidity of the arbitration award in the case of breach of public policy of the State of Bahrain .

109 - Arbitration Act Bahrain issued a decree law No. 9 of 1994, Article No. 31/3 .

110 - Arbitration Act Bahrain issued a decree law No. 9 of 1994, Article 34 .

Third requirement : Arbitration Act Qatari and Sudanese and Yemeni

Review and see the Arbitration Act Sudan for the year 2005 and the Arbitration Act Yemeni issued Presidential Decree Law No. 22 of 1992 and the Arbitration Act Qatari containing the Law of Civil Procedure and the Commercial Part XIII review them and see them show the existence of many of the points and molecules associated with the place and importance of selected do not go out on the whole than previously mentioned in the context of talking about the Saudi regime or Egyptian or Bahrain .

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